

Use of Industrial Robots for Processing Fibre Reinforced Plastics

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Summary

In recent years industrial robots have developed into processing machines with a high grade of mobility and simple programming for reproducible production.

The use of industrial robots in the processing of fibrous composite materials is described by using four examples: fibre spray-up, processing of prepregs, filament winding and postprocessing. Tools and examples of application are described and the special advantages are mentioned.

1. Introduction

During recent years industrial robots have gone through a development which is mostly marked by the advances in microelectronics. The first generation of industrial robots simply had a point-to-point control, where only the starting and finishing point of a movement were defined. The movement in between developed out of the kinematics of the robot. One can easily imagine that the movement of robots with articulated arms, which move all their axes at the same time, differs a lot from a straight line. Since these robots were mainly used for operations such as spot welding, this control was sufficient for these purposes.

The second generation of industrial robots is fitted with continuous-path control and is therefore able to handle superior operations. During a continuous-path control two points are connected with a defined speed and path, which

in the most simple case is a straight line. This requires a large amount of calculation for the control, which became only possible with new microprocessors, since they have higher calculation capacities. Under these conditions it is also possible for the robot to adapt to changed conditions on its own. This happens with the aid of sensors. Their signals are answered by the robot with programmed reactions.

Furthermore modern industrial robots have a computer link, which makes it possible to transfer calculated courses of movements into the robot control. The calculation of the movement sequences can e.g. be made and simulated with CAD-systems.

2. Why using industrial robots?

The special properties of fibrous composite materials can only be used in an optimal manner, when the processing fulfills certain requirements, such as:

- a high reproducibility in the production
- a high precision in the fibre lay-up
- no influence by fouling
- no susceptibility against the partly unhealthy components
- flexible processing with an average number of items.

These requirements are met by modern industrial robots. Additional advantages are:

- single programming
- easy adaption
- low price.

The above mentioned facts are going to be explained with four examples.

3. Fields of application

3.1 Fibre spray-up

Mainly components of a large size are produced in fibre spray-up with average number of mouldings. Compared to other processing methods the material costs are low, because the most inexpensive base materials are used. The mass output is large and the shape of the part can be complicated.

Disadvantages are the strain on the staff by styrene and peroxide, the changing quality of components and the therefore necessary high security factors, which require more material.

When an industrial robot is used for fibre spray-up, as is shown in figure 1, the disadvantages can mostly be sorted out. The regular movements make it possible to calculate the wall thickness t of the laminate in advance from the relationship

$$t = \frac{\dot{m}}{v w \rho}$$

using the velocity v of the robot, the mass output \dot{m} in the spray-up gun, the width w of the jet and the average density ρ .

For a simpler programming it is possible to make diagrams, such as figure 2, with this formula.

For the programming one has to fix an indicator to the spray-up gun, which resembles the centre of the jet. With this indicator points on the path of the component are approached

1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15

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Automated fibre spray-up

fig.1

Calculated diagram for wall thickness

fig.2

and recorded. It is important that the robot realizes malfunctions in the spray-up device as well as running out supplies during the production process. Therefore a connection of signals, as shown in figure 3, is required. Suitable controlling elements are being developed and tested at our institute.

Figure 4 shows what can be achieved with such an equipment: The fluctuations of a wall thickness of 0,6 mm are the most 10 percent, the glas content differs from the average value by 5 percent. This means that large quantities of material can be saved compared to manual processing. The thinnest layer of laminate, which has been sprayed-up at our institute had a wall thickness, which was less than that of a laminated glass mat of 300 g/m² weight per unit area. Therefore the amortization time for such a system is relatively short.

3.2 Prepreg processing

Reproducible, exact processing conditions are most important, because preimpregnated fibrous materials are mainly used for high quality structural parts. Therefore a production for the fin of the Airbus A 310 (see figure 5) is planned, which comprises a great deal of robot work /1/. This includes the bandaging of the module cores, the fixing of the cores to a lattice and the removing of the cores after curing. The precut blanks for the fittings are also to be taken up by the robot from the cutting table and laminated. Since the smallest precut blank is 30 x 50 mm² and the largest is 500 x 700 mm², a gripper with a wide ranging, changeable gripping area is necessary (figure 6). The height of the individual suction elements can be altered and switched on and off so that variable geometries and suction areas result. We chose vacuum grippers because the danger of damaging the material is too great with mechanical grippers.

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Control of fibre spray-up process

fig.3

Produced laminates and processing parameters

fig.4

1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15

Automized Prepreg Processing

Fig.5

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15

Geometry of gripper

fig.6

A further task is the laying-up of the stringer flange. We concipated a tape laying unit for MBB, which fulfills the following requirements:

- Cassette exchange system for variable tape widths
- weight less than 30 kg
- variable cutting angles up to 80° with V-cuts.

The tape laying unit is shown in figure 7 and presently being tested at MBB.

The application of sensors is especially interesting concerning tape laying in order to enable the robot to carry out the task of tape laying with a minimal gap, resp. overlappings. First trials with video cameras /2/ showed that the edge of the tape laid up finally can be identified. This way a sensor is available with which the robot itself can adapt its programmed path.

For tape laying the use of the industrial robot is appropriate where smaller structural components are being produced, since here greater speed and lower operation costs compared to conventional tape laying units can be achieved.

3.3 Filament winding

For the filament winding of geometrically complicated components the industrial robot has the advantage of easier programming and greater mobility /3/ as compared to conventional machines. Since the calculation of the geodesic path on cores without rotational symmetry is still a problem, the teach-in programming is a useful alternative. This way programs for movements can be easily simulated and changed. The high mobility can be read off the number of axes.

Tape laying unit

fig.7

A robot with seven axes is installed in our institute for filament winding, figure 8. Six axes comprise the articulated arm and give the feed-eye all possible degrees of freedom. The seventh axis, serving as a lathe, is in front of the robot. All axes are electrically driven and servo-controlled.

The use of the robot for filament winding was tested on the following components:

- A pipe-T. The programming time could be reduced by a factor of 5 as compared to a conventional filament winding machine.
- A rocker arm for the back wheel of a motorcycle. Here the core partly rotates like "normal" winding, in other program parts the core is not moved; only the feed-eye produces the winding pattern.
- A connecting rod for a motor. Here an automization concept for filament winding was developed. Since the robot is capable of handling peripheral units such as pneumatic cylinders and jaw chucks, it is possible to produce structural components with a robot fully automatically without any additional handling devices. The condition is that the load capacity of robots is not exceeded by the component weight - in our case 45 kg. With the aid of exchange devices for tools an automated production process can then exchange the feed-eye for a gripper and transport the core. By processing input signals, it is further possible to supervise all important processing parameters - filament tension, filling level of resin in the impregnation bath, resin temperature.

Industrial robot for filament winding

fig. 8

3.4 Post-processing

A lot of GRP-structural component series are too small to be post-processed in special devices built for this particular purpose; e.g. motor cycle jackets. Therefore refinishing has to be carried out manually; since, however, the workplace offers bad conditions - dust, noise, monotony -, this leads to high costs resulting from more sick leaves and higher reject rates. The high mobility of a robot is required for the usually three-dimensional mouldings in order to work on all edges without resetting /4/.

For this purpose frequency modulated three-phase milling spindles are suited best, since

- large power with small outer dimensions are realized, this being important for corners which are difficult to reach
- high cutting speeds and therefore high speeds of travel with relatively low forces can be realized
- the armature current provides a measurement signal, which makes supervisions on the load factor of the drive and the wear of the milling cutter possible.

In figure 9, the armature current of a spindle is plotted over the milling path for different hard metal milling cutters. It can be clearly seen that the armature current and therefore the torsional moment steadily increases; at 3.8A or above it is possible that the spindle stops, resp. that the finishing quality is not acceptable anymore. If the armature current is continuously compared to a permissible value (figure 10), then the robot can reduce the speed or stop the processing and exchange the milling cutter should this value be exceeded.

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Wear out of multi-faceted hard metal milling fingers

fig. 9

1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15

Signal-flow graph of milling spindle supervision

fig.10

Since preliminary tests showed that an economical processing is possible with robots, an experiment for larger series is currently being made by a group of eight GRP-processors. Special attention is thereby being paid to the deflashing of SMC-structural components. Here the IKV has made preparatory work with flexible tools and adaptive program corrections.

4. Outlook

In the future the advantage of simple programming of industrial robots will diminish to the evaluated use of CAD-systems for simulating courses of movements; these systems, however, allow the robot programs to be simulated in advance. In connection with off-line programming systems for robots and computer link, the use of robots is facilitated where reproducible production and high mobility with low operation costs and great reliability are required.

Literature

- /1/ Brownbill, D. Aircraft Lightweighting spurs new developments in high-tech composites
Modern Plastics International
3.1982, S. 30 - 33

- /2/ Karpa, L. Automated tape laying of prepregs
Study at IKV 1980, attended by
Dipl.-Ing. W. Ermert

- /3/ Menges, G. Use of industrial robots for
Neise, E. filament winding
40th Annual Conference SPI RP/C
Atlanta '85

- /4/ Menges, G. Automated refinishing with
Neise, E. industrial robots
12. Kunststofftechnisches Kolloquium
Eurogress Aachen 21. - 23.3.1984